

The Role of the Resource Centre in the Development of Environment-Friendly Agriculture in Siana's Sub-District Mandrehe West Nias Regency

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ABSTRACT

Resource Centre is an institution that is engaged in the field of environment friendly agricultural training located in West Nias Regency. Established since 2007 and has been carrying out extensive socialization and training and provides direct examples of environmentally friendly farming without chemical fertilizers (inorganic) in the land of Resource Centre Training and socialization that was provided in the form of cultivation, composting, pesticides, natural and reinforcement for the personal and group. The changes of agriculture to modern agriculture, eventually humans become less wise and not friendly with nature and the environment. Environmentally friendly farming is hopeful for farmers as producers and as consumers. Some of the obstacles that faced by is still a low the low understanding of the farmers against the application of environment-friendly agricultural system, lack of information, training and attention of local governments in expanding it. This research was conducted in the village of Siana's sub-district Mandrehe West Nias Regency. Methods of analysis that used in this research are qualitative descriptive analysis with total samples 116 heads of families. The results showed has not been successfully Resource Centre plays a role in developing environmentally-friendly agriculture in the surrounding of due villages, has limited funds and time because they were focus on their own land as local business. The response of the villagers around the Resource Centre plays a part in the cultivation, manufacture, compost fertilizer, pesticides and marketing of agricultural products, the development of environment-friendly agriculture in the village of Siana's has not been successfully involved because of the existence of group that can be directly enjoyed by the citizens. Support from Government has not been programmed because the limitations of human and financial resources.

Keywords: Institution Resource Centre, Community Response, Support From The Government.

INTRODUCTION

Changes in agriculture are currently undergoing very significant changes, from traditional agriculture to modern agriculture. The high productivity of plants with the presence of superior seeds, the fertility of plants due to the use of chemical fertilizers, and the elimination of plant pests due to the

efficacy of pesticides have placed humans as winners against nature. Humans eventually become unwise, and become unfriendly to nature and the environment. Nature that has become a place of human habitation has been forgotten and ignored by the act of carelessness. As a result of this exploitation, nature then loses balance

which ultimately has a negative impact on humans. The use of pesticides intended to eradicate pests and diseases has been proven to cause pollution to the environment and directly or indirectly disrupt human health (Fardiaz, 1992).

Learning from the negative effects above, humans then tried to find techniques to plant safely, both for the environment and humans. This is what later gave birth to the technique of planting organically or environmentally friendly agriculture. Organic farming is a farming activity that is familiar with the environment which can minimize negative impacts on the surrounding environment. The main characteristic of organic agriculture is the use of local varieties that are relatively still natural, followed by the use of organic fertilizers and organic pesticides. Organic agriculture is a guide for the times; lately human awareness to preserve the environment has increased. Therefore it is necessary to develop agricultural cultivation without the use of dangerous chemical fertilizers. Humans as end consumers of agricultural products will feel safe and secure in their health (Andoko, 2010).

Modern agriculture that is instantaneous makes farmers in carrying out their farming business want a lot of results in a short time and not too much trouble. Conventional farmers assume that if they cultivate organically there are many difficulties that will be faced. One of them is that conventional farmers have concerns that they will have difficulty in obtaining organic fertilizer. The farmers have not seen the local potential in the form of agricultural waste and livestock manure which are abundantly available which can be managed into organic fertilizer. Organic fertilizers are seen as troublesome and require more energy to manage and use them. Likewise, the various plants that can be used as organic pesticides are no longer widely used because besides the limited knowledge of farmers, they are also seen as something that is troublesome. Awareness of managing the environment for the better is often defeated

by considerations of technical convenience (Avelinus, 2008). The limited knowledge, attitudes and skills of farmers, greatly affect the ability to try better farming. In order for the farming community to believe that the organic farming system can provide benefits for both agricultural productivity and land productivity, awareness must be taken first. Growing public awareness will foster motivation to adopt technology with organic systems or natural ways.

According to Mardikanto (2009) the main actors of agricultural development in Indonesia are actually small farmers, small farmers, small farmers and small fishermen who are generally weak economic groups, which are not only weak in capital / asset ownership and other production factors, but especially weak knowledge, skills and often weak in his attitude to advance for the betterment of his destiny. The presence of non-governmental organizations and the role of agricultural extension agents in the midst of farming communities in the village is still very much needed to improve human resources (farmers) so that they can manage existing natural resources intensively in order to achieve increased productivity and income or achieve food security and economic resilience.

Farmers need to have training centers to foster them independently, structured, sustainably managed for the benefit of the farmers themselves. Basically the institution is a social group as a set of people who hold regular face-to-face relationships because they have a common goal and attitude.

The institution itself is in the form of a government institution which is under the control of the government and non-governmental institutions, both private and non-governmental organizations. Agricultural non-governmental organizations usually conduct agricultural counseling through organizing local communities, providing advocacy, organizing training, mentoring. Along with the declining role of counseling and the decreasing image of education carried out by the government,

the existence of non-agricultural institutions is increasingly recognized and built collaborative cooperation between government agricultural extension institutions and private parties.

Non-governmental organizations (Mardikanto, 2009). The collaboration will facilitate the development of farms managed by farmers. Likewise with facilities provided by institutions for farmers, these facilities can help farmers develop their farming and lead to the independence of farmers. The activities carried out by farmers in the village of Siana'a in order to develop organic farming cannot be separated from the role of the Institute Resource Center, both in the implementation process and in the stages of making natural fertilizers and pesticides.

The Resource Center is a private institution that plays a role and engages in the field of environmentally friendly agricultural training in accordance with the stages in farming, the Resource Center is located in West Nias Regency, Mandrehe Village, Siana'a Village. The Resource Center in West Nias was established in 2007 and has conducted many trainings and provided examples of environmentally friendly agriculture that do not use chemical fertilizers (inorganic), nor serve students in industrial work practices (internship) for SMK students in the Department of Agriculture, but there is currently no significant development agricultural products, especially the area around the location of the Resource Center. Some supporting facilities for implementing activities in the Resource Center are: 1). Compost machine, 2). Filter machine Compost, 3). Coconut Belt Machine, 4). Lawn mower, 5). Water pump.

The role and function of the Institute Resource Center as a forum for farmer organizations is still not running optimally. This situation is caused by various factors, including only a small number of human resources of institutional actors, the low quality of human resources of the institutional actors and facilities provided by

the Institute of Resource Centers is still lacking. The role of the Resource Center Institute in developing organic farming is interesting to study, to find out how much the Resource Center contributes to the development of organic farming in the village area of Siana'a.

Based on the above background, it is interesting to examine the Role of Resource Centers in the development of environmentally friendly agriculture in West Nias Regency, so to further put forward a study entitled "Role Resource Center In Development Agriculture Friendly Environment In Village Siana'a Sub-District Mandrehe, West Nias District".

RESEARCH METHODS

This research is a descriptive study where the method of collecting data through surveys, interviews, questionnaires. The location or location of the study is Siana'a Village, Mandrehe District, West Nias Regency.

Population is the number of collections of all elements to be concluded (Indrawan R and Yarniawati, 2014). The population in this study were all villagers of Siana'a, namely 172 heads of families. While the sample in this study is the head of the family whose daily workers are farmers with a total of 116 heads of families, the sample determination by the census method is the total number of samples.

Table 3.1. The condition of the residents of Siana'a Village, Mandrehe District, West Nias Regency

No	Work	Total/KK	Percentage (%)
1	PNS/TNI/POLRI	21 KK	12,20 %
2	Petani	116 KK	67,44 %
3	Jasa	19 KK	11,05 %
4	Wiraswasta	16 KK	09,30 %
Total			

The data in this study consisted of primary data and secondary data. Primary data obtained by observation, questionnaires, and interviews.

In addition to observations and questionnaires, interviews were conducted by means of discussions with stakeholders, interviewees and agricultural agencies to find out the problems and obstacles faced in

implementing environmentally friendly agriculture.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Role Of Resource Centers In The Development Of Environmentally Friendly Agriculture.

In order to introduce and develop environmentally friendly agriculture in the West Nias district, the Resource Center (RC) held socialization through churches, schools, and meetings held by the community, besides the Resource Center (RC) also educated the next generation to prepare and equip Vocational school students majoring in Food Crops and Horticulture (ATPH) in order to become a reliable and qualified generation to build a nation especially in agriculture are moral responsibilities of both educational institutions (schools) and the Business World / Industrial World and Society institutions. Answering this challenge, the Sibolga Caritas Keuskupan Resource Center (RC) was present, working with the school to facilitate, assist, foster and direct vocational students, especially ATPH majors through Industrial Work Practices (Prakerin) at the village Resource Center Siana'a Mandrehe District, West Nias Regency.

This Prakerin activity lasted for three months. The method of implementing apprenticeship is 30% theory and 70% practice. With this method, students are expected to be able to understand, understand and master the fields of activity carried out while in the location of the Business World / Industrial World. During the practice on the RC, the students did several things, one of which was the development of a young plant demoplot. Growing, growing, and producing, that's what is always expected from plants. Therefore, one of the factors that influence this is good soil management. To get a loose soil structure, the soil needs to be processed. One way is by hoeing. Loose soil structure is very good for plant root growth. Roots can freely absorb nutrients in the soil. If the

roots grow well and are healthy, plant growth will be fast, fertile and many fruits. This very basic and important concept must be understood and mastered by every student who engages in RC.

Another thing they did was making organic fertilizer (compost), developing demoplot perennials (cocoa and grafting rubber), grafting PB 260 grafting rubber nurseries, and pig farms. It is expected that the existence of a Resource Center as a House for Integrated Farming and Training in Animal Husbandry Development can bring positive benefits to all levels of society, especially young people who are tasting education at school. The participation of CKS through RC to participate in educating the next generation, especially in agriculture, does not stop here, for 2013 there have been two schools that will entrust their students to the RC, namely State Vocational School 1 Mandrehe and Vocational School 1 Ulu Moro'o . The Resource Center activity (RC) is a special unit owned by Sibolga Caritas Keuskupan (CKS) which functions as a place for integrated agricultural education / training facilities. Initially it was intended for the CKS-assisted group community, but in its development RC opened itself as a place of learning and training for various groups of the general public. Some activities carried out on RC: 1). Agricultural development Hard plants (rubber, cocoa, fruit, productive wood) Young crops (development of young plant demoplots with a rotation system, cultivation of crops and food crops with monoculture and agroforestry systems) Production Gardens Development of organic fertilizers and manufacture of MOL 2). Education / Training Facilities 3). RC independence. RC service works are considered to have an impact on the community in West Nias. CKS and the Holy Cross Parish, West Nias agreed to continue this work.

At this time the support of several international Caritas families gradually declined. So, in order to continue working, RC needs to raise its own funds by

providing agricultural training services and producing several plant / tree seeds for sale to the community, namely: Grafting rubber seeds (PB 260 clones) ready for planting / stem Entres / meters, Mahogany / stems , In addition to the above plant / tree seeds, RC has also started breeding local species, crosses, and duroc (hybrid). Also available to sell for / kilogram of body weight. Hopefully in the future, RC will truly be able to become a center for the development of human and natural resources, RC can be an example for the general public through the results of testing and experiments. Until now, RC's work in the world of agriculture can be said to be quite good. Besides being one of the units at CKS, RC is also able to become a learning house for the community, and the community is also given the freedom to duplicate the models they have seen in RC to do on their own land. For its success, collaboration between: local administration, the government is needed

Organizing such as division of labor, division of small units and determination of the line of authority carried out by farmers themselves, in terms of organizing farmers in the village of Siana'a The Resource Center institution did not intervene. Resource Center provides direction and advice in terms of organizing, which is then left to farmers, because the capabilities and weaknesses of individual farmers who know it are farmers themselves if organizing is done by farmers themselves. It will be easier and directed. The Resource Center's goal of providing direction and organizing is to be overlapping, all farmers have their respective responsibilities, communication becomes smooth, coordination between farmers is also good, the process runs as planned, and can minimize problems. The assistance of the Resource Center Institute in terms of organizing which only conducts direction and input is intended to enable the participant farmer to be directly involved in coordinating (planning, implementing and evaluating) and in giving decisions (deciding something) to choose various conditions in organizing.

The Resource Center runs the work of service to the community for those in need, with the aim of taking part and taking part in reducing poverty, so that they can get the same rights as other people such as education, employment, food, and health services. With the presence of the Resource Center, it is expected to grow the interest of the community to actively farm, especially young plants that do not require a long time to obtain results, and do not have to depend on expensive chemical fertilizers, but only by utilizing existing natural resources and then processed in such a way appearance to be used again as fertilizers or organic fertilizers (compost). The Resource Center provides its own example of its dilation that it can successfully cultivate young plants without the use of chemical fertilizers, and this institution is open to anyone who wants to learn about how to farm without chemical fertilizers that are more environmentally friendly. If the community can succeed through farming, then to fulfill the same rights as other people can be fulfilled.

Awareness that needs to be built on farmers is awareness of community / groups that grow on the basis of needs, not coercion and encouragement of certain projects. The objectives are (1) to organize the power of farmers in fighting for their rights, (2) obtain bargaining positions and accurate market information, especially related to the prices of agricultural products and (3) play a role in negotiating and determining the prices of agricultural products produced by its members (Masmulyadi,2007).

The Response Of The Village Farmers Community Of Siana'a To The Activities Of The Resource Center.

The Siana'a village farmer community knows the existence of the Resource Center in the midst of their village but does not know of the activities carried out within the institution, the information on its initial existence varies, there are those who see directly when passing and also hear from relatives or relatives. In general, people do not know about the activities carried out in Resource Centralization

because there are still very few people who have ever visited to see firsthand the activities carried out within the institution. The community was not very enthusiastic at first exploring the types of activities in the Resource Center institutions due to its first activities, namely seeding rubber grafting and after being sold to interested people, the community's view of grafting rubber had not yet fully accepted the respective fields in changing old rubber land, traditional rubber switch to new rubber grafting rubber land, because there are so many work processes and fertilizers that can cost a lot. As well as on the other hand informants circulated to residents that the age of grafting rubber should not be recycled for long compared to old rubber, namely traditional rubber, although the sap is only a little but has a long life and does not sprinkle fertilizer in cleaning just by clearing the land.

Very few people in the village of Siana'a have large areas of land to be used as organic crops such as in the Resource Center, because in general the surrounding communities have been filled with rubber trees as their main source of income, only 12.1% of the heads of farm families are able to own land empty area to be used as organic farming land for young plants as carried out in the Resource Center, this is what makes people's interest in gardening or farming sustainably / organically to be very low due to the narrow land factor which has been contaminated with chemicals due to the excessive use of chemical fertilizers, the soil has hardened.

Land for organic farming must be free of residues from fertilizers and synthetic chemical drugs. The process of converting land from conventional agriculture to organic farming takes at least 1-3 years. During the transition period, the agricultural products produced cannot be said to be organic because they usually still contain chemical residues. Another thing that must be considered is the environment around the land. Chemical pollution from neighboring gardens can damage the organic farming system that has been built.

Pollutants can move to our organic land because they are carried by water and air. In addition to pollutants, the use of drugs from neighboring gardens can cause pests and diseases to run into organic farms. Of course pests will look for lands that are free of toxins, and unfortunately organic gardens will become easy targets. To get around this, you can use hedgerows. Some types of hedgerows have the ability to absorb odors, chemicals, and pest repellents. In addition, forages from hedgerows can be used as organic fertilizer.

Farmers who use 25.9% organic fertilizer for complex reasons and too much work and take a long time to make compost plus their livestock cages which are mostly still in an emergency condition are finally difficult to collect livestock manure because they are scattered everywhere there is no one way out the manure can be used as compost fertilizer. Actually, the farming community is dependent, if someone is dependent on something, even if they know the bad effects of something. then they will be difficult regardless of dependency. of course it takes a process and hard work to be able to change it. Like the case with the farming community in Indonesia in general and Nias in particular those who are still dependent on using chemical fertilizers. if not based on intention, we can imagine what we will inherit for our children and grandchildren later. Below is the impact of dependence on the use of chemical fertilizers.

Only awareness will move our farmers to use organic fertilizer again. Awareness is directly proportional to one's knowledge. It is time for young intellectuals to take to the field to provide knowledge to farmers how important it is to use organic fertilizer. Dilemma, when farmers' children are told to study at school but their knowledge is not used for community welfare. There is a chain of knowledge lost between the current generation and the previous generation. Even though these two generations should complement each other. Institutions as rules of the game (rule of game) and organizations play an important

role in regulating the use / allocation of resources efficiently, evenly and sustainably. According to Elizabeth and Darwis (2003), rural institutions were born to meet the social needs of the community. Its nature is not linear, but tends to be the individual needs of its members, in the form of: physical needs, security needs, social relations needs, recognition, and development of recognition. The main benefit of the institution is to accommodate the needs of one side of society's social life, and as social control, so that everyone can regulate their behavior according to the wishes of the community.

Residents who had attended training and counseling and learned farming in the Resource Center about environmentally friendly organic farming were still relatively low compared to the heads of farmer families 11.2% said they were (yes), while others said no. From the number of farmers in the village of Siana'a, the Resource Center has started working on plant cultivation without the use of chemical fertilizers, composting to be used as fertilizers, artificial pesticides and how to process the land, but the intention of the local community is very low, according to them Organic farming that is environmentally friendly requires a long time and adequate facilities are different from the Resource Center institutions that have sufficient facilities to implement it.

On the other hand, usually at the beginning of starting a business or work is always haunted by a sense of anxiety succeeding because if they do not succeed, then they are difficult to eat, not to mention the garden / newly opened land is usually very high attacked by pests, to be immune and adjust with these pests it takes a rather long process, as is the case with land that has been contaminated by the use of chemical fertilizers so far it takes approximately three years to recover. While the Resource Center even though they failed they could still eat everyday because their employees were employees of the diocese of Sibolga.

The Resource Center has conducted training on organic farming that is environmentally friendly or without the use of chemical fertilizers in the surrounding villages and also provides examples of direct farming in locations where the Resource Center can be witnessed by the surrounding community, but the surrounding community is very minimal who is enthusiastic about doing, learning and imitating what has been proven by the Resource Center because the community around the level of education is still very low, the majority have not attended school and graduated from elementary school, besides that they feel very busy farming like that. The acceptance of the surrounding community is very minimal because the paradigm that still tends to be practical and fast farming as well as many and short-term results without regard to the preservation of nature in the future and healthy food free of chemical residues.

As a small part of the Siana'a village farmers have gained knowledge about how to make compost that can be used as organic fertilizer to replace use rather than chemical fertilizers, but not all farmers who use organic fertilizer / compost know from the way the Resource Center makes it only 22.4%, but there are farmers who learn on their own via the internet, buy books and a small portion of the experience of working relatives. Farmers in the village of Siana'a whose majority of education is not yet in school and only graduated (Elementary School) Elementary School is one of the inhibiting factors for wanting to learn how to make relatively little organic fertilizer because understanding and knowledge of the dangers of using chemical fertilizers has not been understood. Back to the awareness of each farmer to keep the environment and the environment which is then inherited for future generations. And it is necessary from various parties, including government, schools, institutions, and the other to provide information about the dangers of using chemical fertilizers but move our farmers to re-use environmentally friendly

organic fertilizers. Awareness is directly proportional to one's knowledge. It is time for young intellectuals to take to the field in providing knowledge to farmers how important it is to use organic fertilizer. Dilemma, when farmers' children are told to study at school but their knowledge is not used for community welfare. Another was eliminated from the minimalist community who continued their studies in agriculture because they thought that after graduation they returned to being farmers whose work was always dirty and dirty.

Siana'a village farmers who can make and use natural pesticides 22, 4% are still relatively small in number of farmers who know the making of natural / vegetable pesticides, because there are very few interest in using them because of the long process and many ways of working, and knowledge to make it unknown what ingredients are needed, because the lack of information obtained coupled with a very low level of education to find information is limited because some farmers cannot read. Wargayang, a farmer in Siana'a village, knows how to make natural / vegetable pesticides not only from the Resource Center but through friends who used to farm organically and most of the information is inherited from old-time parents.

If we want to live healthy and environmentally friendly, there is a choice or option offered, namely to use "natural ingredients" to drive away or drive out natural enemies that attack plants, without having to turn them off, so that the ecosystem cycle is still maintained. ecological and environmentally friendly by using organic / natural pesticides. As one of the solutions in natural and integrated pest management that is processed naturally and is multipurpose. not only used for eradicating pests but more focused on preventing and protecting plants and conditioning plants to be resistant to any pest attack.

Cultivating land for organic farming is cleaning up the area to be planted, the first step is to open a plot of land to be used as an

agricultural area. Can be done by cutting grass and cutting down wild trees that are not needed. The remainder of the cleaning plant should not be burned but collected somewhere and waited until it is dry. For better, all the rest is cut into small pieces so that it can be used in the composting process. Please note that grass roots are also good for the plants you want to develop. Because in all the roots contained bacteria that symbiosis mutualism to produce the nutrients needed. Further excavation is carried out by extracting as deep as 20-30 cm. After excavating, it should be mixed with animal manure or ditch soil. Do it while stretching and breaking the parts into smaller pieces. This treatment is useful for enriching organic and inorganic materials in soil which may have been lost before being used or carried by erosion. Then make beds that are higher than the ground level with a certain size. The beds are made higher so that the surface water flow caused by the rain is not flooded and brings nutrients. So land processing is absolutely necessary to create a fairly good environment. (Kanisius, 1983). The Siana'a village farmer community said how to cultivate their land knowing from previous ancestor habits that have been handed down to the current generation, only 23% knew it from the Resource Center through training and direct observation of visiting times or around the location of the institution.

Resource Cent before forming a farmer group in Siana'a village was not yet included in the Resource Center program. The Resource Center is a place for anyone who wants to learn to farm organically which is more environmentally friendly, if the Resource Center forms a group it is feared that it will take a lot of time in mentoring even though there are only 3 (three) people who have responsibility in caring for and maintaining Planting in the Resource Center as the main task is to get maximum results and then sell it as a business that has been paid to the manager. Furthermore, inevitably need funds in mentoring and guidance groups, not to

mention the presumption of the farming community today if there is a group formed by one of the institutions hoping for assistance in the form of money or free seeds.

The Resource Center seldom makes direct observations of individual farms, but if it crosses the land / gardens of the surrounding community, the Resource Center will always stop and tell about the agriculture carried out by the community, if there is a problem or complaint that is conveyed by the community this information will be a solution for the advancement of agriculture in West Nias in general. The institutional role of Resource Cent for farmers is very important, where agricultural institutions support a lot of business opportunities carried out by a person or farmer group itself. It is not separated that the institutions of farmers and farmers are an inseparable unit.

Efforts That Can Be Made By Stakeholders Of The Agriculture Service In West Nias In Implementing Environmentally Friendly Agriculture.

Realize the realization of an organic farming system for the realization of sustainable agriculture, the role of the Government and Institutions in agriculture is very important. The role of the government in terms of certification is certainly highly expected so that consumers have confidence in the results of organic agricultural products so that eventually the farmers want to strive to implement an organic farming system. The role of Agencies in agriculture, such as holding agricultural counseling and field schools is very important. With the extension of the organic farming system itself, the teaching of making organic fertilizers, the introduction of organic Integrated Pest Management (IPM) and the introduction of vegetable and biological pesticides to farmers, can at least increase farmers' awareness of the importance of organic farming systems so that in the end they want to implement and even develop the organic

farming system. Indonesia as an agrarian country with rich natural products and prospective commodities for organic agriculture can actually develop a good organic farming system as long as there is awareness and willingness from Indonesian farmers and support from the Government and the agencies concerned.

Starting from the formation of West Nias, until now, the relevant government agencies have not yet programmed sustainable agricultural development for the farming communities of West Nias district, with the background of human resources that are still very limited. Efforts to realize sustainable agricultural development in Indonesia in addition to starting from government initiatives and institutional pressures carried out by the wider community itself, also need the full development of human resources (Anwar 2005).

In addition, the regional budget is still low, so that it prioritizes the building of buildings and infrastructure for the continuity of all government activities in West Nias Regency. To promote environmentally friendly agriculture in West Nias district, government support is needed, both for institutions, groups and other people who need to be provided specifically about environmentally friendly agriculture in order to achieve prosperous and healthy farmers.

Government intervention in the future development of agricultural institutions is still needed. However, the form of government interference is not cohesive, but rather facilitating so that it can stimulate cohesive institutional growth. Rules that develop on local institutions should be leadership with rules and laws related to existing institutions (Suradisastira, 2008).

The resource center does not approach the empowerment of surrounding rural farmers because the time and opportunity of Resource center employees is very limited because they must continue to carry out their duties within the institution to maintain

growing plants, raise livestock, maintain facilities such as machinery and compost and some other tasks ministry of pastors to stations (churches).

In addition to the obstacles above Resource center does not carry out empowerment to the farming community is the problem of funding or funding plus problems that are often faced in the field, farmers who always expect all institutions to even expect assistance in terms of plant seeds, especially in the form of money economic factors farmers who are still very low and have a narrow mindset because of the relatively low education and habits after the earthquake in Nias that came from all directions.

Support From Parties In The Development Of Organic Farming

Agricultural farming development is not only done by farmers, but there are several parties involved in developing organic rice farming (stakeholders). Each party has its own role in developing organic farming, the parties involved in developing organic farming are farmers, Institution Resource Centers, business people, Field Extension Officers and mass media in the form of regional newspapers.

1) Farmers

Farmers are the core stakeholders in the development of inorganic farms in the village that have direct links with interests in a policy or program. Core stakeholders as the main determinant in the decision making process. Farmers as the main actors in organic farming carry out their role in cultivating the results of farming, from the selection of seeds to harvest, which is maintained as truly organic yields. In addition to conducting organic cultivation, farmers also provide supervision to other farmers related to the implementation of organic farming on their land. Another role expected from farmers is to help invite other farmers to participate in implementing organic farming.

2) Business Actors

Business people are also stakeholders in the development of organic farming in the

village, business people are one of the parties who seek for commercial purposes. Participating in organic farming is the marketer of organic products, namely traditional markets / local markets, as product marketers (helping market products) not only selling products from farmers to consumers, but also providing information on market needs and pricing information to farmers. Prices given to farmers are in accordance with current market prices, but because there is no certification of prices pegged will be the same as non-organic. Business people in the development of inorganic farms can play a role in promoting and channeling or selling organic products. Promotions of organic products can be done by organic product stores, while marketing them can be done by traditional markets or existing ones, Sutanto (2002).

3) PPL (Field Extension Officer)

PPL is a supporting stakeholder, namely a stakeholder who does not have a direct relationship with a policy or program.

However, they have concern and concern so that they share and influence the attitude of the community. PPL is an extension officer on duty in the field, the role of PLPL in developing organic farming that is environmentally friendly and provides information when there is a program from the government. Agricultural extension workers are field extension officers (PPL) who play an important role in the development of organic agriculture. The role is as a companion of farmers and promoting organic farming. This farmer assistance will also be assisted by the Community Empowerment Institute and the farmers themselves as the main actors (Sutanto 2002).

4) Mass media

Mass media is a supporting stakeholder, namely stakeholders who have no direct interest, but indirectly give their attention. Mass media is one of the parties that gives and disseminates information to those who access it. The use of regional news letters in the development of organic farming in the village of Siana'a has not been able to run

optimally, information given from the newspaper itself is general in nature and does not only inform specifically for organic farming.

5) Resource Center

The Resource Center Institution is also a supporting stakeholder. The Resource Center plays several roles in organic farming in Siana'a Village, including providing training to farmers, selling compost, forming organic farmer groups and helping to market organic produce. In addition to the role that has been carried out, the Institute of Resource Centers is expected to be able to work with the government in developing organic farming.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

CONCLUSION

The existence of the Resource Center has carried out its role as an environmentally friendly agricultural developer in the village of Siana'a by conducting socialization, plant cultivation training, strengthening farmer capacity, organizing. Planting directly in the land as an example to the community as well as helping with marketing of farm produce even though it is not fully full is due to more farming and self-determination in its location which is nothing but the ultimate goal as a local business or business.

Siana'a village farmers' views on the existence of Resource Centers in their villages, the role of these institutions is still low in developing environmentally friendly agriculture with the background of only 22.4% participating in organic farming and learning from the Resource Center plus the absence of groups formed for example in their villages that can be directly benefited by the community rely solely on the example of the resource center itself.

The relevant government has not been able to do anything in developing environmentally friendly agriculture in West Nias due to the very limited human and financial resources plus new blooming

districts that need large funds for other priority activities.

Recommendations

The Resource Center needs to make more breakthroughs and a lot of socialization to the surrounding community so that they are better known and understand how to farm environmentally friendly

The Siana'a village farming community should be able to see and visit the Resource Center more often to be able to discuss with the officials there about environmentally friendly farming methods to preserve the nature that is needed by future generations.

Stackholders or related parties need to prepare human resources in charge of organic agriculture or environmentally friendly agriculture for the advancement of farmers in West Nias such as providing scholarships for agriculture, sending people to study outside Nias island to further enhance the experience.

Resource Centers and Stackholders Prepare superior seedlings of commodity crops.

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How to cite this article: Gulo, S, Nasution, Z. et al. The role of the resource centre in the development of environment-friendly agriculture in Siana's sub-district Mandrehe West Nias regency. International Journal of Research and Review. 2019; 6(5):262-273.
